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MECHANISMS FOR INCREASING WOMEN'S ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

***Abstract:** This article focuses on mechanisms for increasing women's activism in Uzbekistan, highlighting women's active participation in state and public life as part of ongoing reforms, as well as their important role in the country's political processes. In particular, the main factors of women's activity in the political, economic, and social spheres, as well as their participation in legislative initiatives and reforms, are examined. Special attention is paid to the issues of gender equality in their activities in state structures and international organizations. The study of this topic reveals the mechanisms that promote gender equality of women in society, their spiritual and intellectual support, and their participation in public administration and politics in Uzbekistan. In addition, emphasis is placed on empowering women and ensuring their active participation in decision-making processes.*

***Keywords:** Women, mechanisms, legislation, public administration, political participation, gender equality, statistics, education, activism.*

Introduction

In modern society, an important role is played by increasing the activity of women. Dear President of our country Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev noted: "We must actively continue the state policy to protect the health of mothers and children, ensure employment, taking into account the living conditions of women, increase the role and authority of women in social and political life. We consider this our main duty." [Sh. M. Mirziyoyev, 2018, 39 p.] In our country, laws and state programs are being implemented aimed at increasing the activity of women in socio-political and cultural life, stimulating economic development, protecting their rights and interests, improving education and qualifications, acquiring professions and employment, as well as expanding their opportunities in the formation of civil society.

Greater involvement of women in social and political life by creating equal opportunities for their personal development in society not only increases their importance in their lives, but also creates a solid foundation for national development.

Main part

Today, in Uzbekistan, the increase in the activity of women in public life is considered as one of the key indicators of the country's development. In our country,

the protection of the rights and interests of women, ensuring their active participation in all areas have been elevated to the rank of state policy. By the Decree of the President of our country “On measures to further improve the system of supporting women and ensuring their active participation in society”, No. PI-5020, dated March 5, 2021 was approved. In accordance with this decree: the goals were set to increase the participation of women in all spheres of the country’s economic, political, and social life, to provide comprehensive assistance in obtaining education, developing professional skills, and ensuring employment, to further support entrepreneurial initiatives, to create “Women’s Register” at the local level, and to systematically study, analyze, and resolve the problems, needs, and interests of women included in them, thus bringing this work to a qualitatively new level.[2]

The activity of women in public administration in Uzbekistan has become increasingly significant in recent years, and their participation in social, political, and economic life has grown. This process is being carried out by the country's leadership as part of reforms aimed at ensuring gender equality and supporting and strengthening women's rights.

Moreover, Article 58 of the Constitution of our country states: “Women and men shall have equal rights.

The State shall ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the administration of public and state affairs and in other spheres of social and state life.” [3]

On September 2, 2019, the Law “On guarantees with respect to equal rights and opportunities for women and men” was adopted.[4] The Law “On protection of women from harassment and abuse” was also passed. In accordance with Article 5 of the Law “The main directions of the state policy in the field of protecting women from harassment and abuse”;

The main directions of the state policy in the field of protecting women from harassment and abuse shall be as follows:

- developing and implementing a gender policy, state programs and strategies in the field of protecting women from harassment and abuse;

- creating the atmosphere of intolerance to harassment and abuse of women in the society;

- ensuring protection of rights, freedoms and legal interests of women from harassment and abuse;

- enhancing legal awareness and legal culture in the society, strengthening the rule of law;

- creating effective organizational and legal mechanisms to prevent, reveal, eliminate harassment and abuse of women;

- taking measures to eradicate reasons and conditions which promote harassment and abuse of women;

- ensuring cooperation between state bodies, self-governing bodies of citizens, non-governmental non-profit organizations and other civil society institutions in order to prevent harassment and abuse has been established.[5]

As you know, the concepts and values of “Human-Family-Society-State” play an important role in the life of every country and every people. Without women, it is impossible to imagine the fundamental structure of society and family. As the First President of our country, Islam Abduganievich Karimov, said: “Those who unite our family and society, bring grace and blessings to them, and instill love, kindness, and compassion in our homes, are truly our revered mothers and sisters. Reason, kindness, and compassion keep the family balanced, pure, honest, sincere, and just. Honoring motherhood is a quality elevated to the highest value in our society. The more we treat women as the light of our lives, the colors of our existence, the more we will respect our families and our homeland.”[6]

The resolution of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, approved by SI-297-IV “About the approval of the strategy of achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” dated May 21, 2021, is also aimed at ensuring equal participation of women in public administration and increasing their social and political activity. Chapter IV of this resolution, titled “Priorities of gender strategy implementation” includes Section II on “Ensuring Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men in the field of Public Service” which states: “In order to ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the field of public service, it is necessary to implement the following measures” in accordance with this Code, namely:

- to gradually increase the share of women in leadership positions by introducing the mechanisms of appointment to leadership positions of state bodies based on competitions;

- to strengthen the participation of women in solving socio-political issues in the life of society and in making decisions of urgent importance and in their implementation;

- to expand the opportunity of women to represent the state and the state body and organization in which they operate at the international level, and to participate in the work of international organizations;

- expansion of the practice of solving the problems that concern the population directly by women working in leadership positions;

- increase their activity in the socio-economic development of regions by expanding the practice of appointing women to leadership positions of local executive authorities;

- development of criteria for ensuring gender equality aimed at creating equal opportunities for promotion in state bodies and organizations based on the experience of advanced foreign countries;

- establishing systematic measures to improve the qualifications of women recommended for leadership positions in public authorities and management bodies at the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- to establish a system of training, retraining and upgrading the qualifications of experts on gender-legal examination of normative legal documents and their drafts;

-keeping information on the ratio of the number of women and men working in relevant positions in state bodies and organizations;

-strengthening the legal basis for conducting gender audits in state bodies and organizations based on a comprehensive gender approach, developing its principles, is planned.[7]

In the “Election Code” of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted in 2019, it is stipulated that the proportion of women among candidates for deputies must be 40 percent. In a single-mandate constituency, candidates will be nominated by political parties based on a party list.”[8]

Considerable attention is given to the training of women, their career guidance, and professional development. In particular, the Law of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated August 18, 2022, “On Measures to Streamline the Allocation of Educational Loans for the Training of Women in Higher, Secondary Special, and Vocational Educational Organizations on a Paid-Contract Basis” was adopted. The provision of this law stipulates that the principal debt on loans provided to women is to repayment of the main debt of the educational loan by the borrower within 7 years, starting from the seventh month after the end of the period of formal study of the relevant type of education in the educational organization.[9]

In Uzbekistan, the proportion of women in parliament reached 34.6 percent in 2023, compared to 6.0 percent in 1995. Although Uzbekistan introduced a 30 percent gender quota for parliamentary elections in 2004, this figure increased to 40 percent in 2023.[10]

In our country, cooperation with international organizations on women's rights issues is underway, and programs and projects related to women's rights are being implemented. The role of women in public and non-governmental organizations is being strengthened.

In conclusion, as emphasized by the President, “Currently, every woman must not only be an observer of democratic processes, but also an active initiator.” From this, it follows that the opportunities and reforms being created for women in Uzbekistan are aimed at enhancing their activity.

The reforms being implemented in our country place great emphasis on increasing women's participation. Women are being provided with ample opportunities to actively participate in state governance, demonstrate their capabilities in various fields, enhance their influence in social life, ensure their rights, and contribute to the overall development of the state.

One of the most important aspects in increasing women's socio-political activity in society is identifying the following key criteria: purposefulness, hard work, determination, initiative, willpower, honesty, integrity, loyalty, a deep sense of high responsibility and personal accountability, good health, and a healthy lifestyle. With these criteria in mind, expanding the ranks of active women is one of the main tasks. The current reforms serve to further enhance their role in the socio-political life of the country.

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